

Jamal J. Elias. *After Rumi: The Mevlevis and Their World*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2025. 288 p., ISBN: 9780674296145.

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Jamal Elias' *After Rumi: The Mevlevis and Their World* offers a narrative of Mevlevi self-presentation over the course of four centuries. Thoughtfully engaging with biographical dictionaries and commentaries on the *Masnavi*, Elias argues that the Mevlevis "developed a distinctive emotional style based around Rumi and his writings."¹ This emotional style was enacted in Persian and was neither wholly "heterodox" nor "orthodox"—two sub-claims of the book that I will flesh out in this review. Pitched to a general audience, the book does a nice job of unfolding a narrative of Mevlevi self-presentation clearly. However, it could more effectively intervene into scholarly debates within Persian literary studies or the study of Sufism, which I will touch on below. Such an intervention would aid its attempts at a critical approach to gender in general and masculinity in particular. Despite these shortcomings, the book succeeds in providing an accessible account of Mevlevi self-presentation that is not divorced from dynamics of power both internal to Mevlevi kinship and external within Anatolian and Ottoman society. It follows the Mevlevis from their origins to their establishment of power in Ottoman Istanbul and their incorporation of diverse strands of Islamic thought by the 17th century. The first four chapters focus on origins, alternating between historically locating the Mevlevis in chapters one and three, and analyzing the sources that describe two formative figures, Rumi and his grandson Ulu 'Arif Chelebi, in chapters two and four. The fifth chapter pushes the chronological arc forward to the 17th century, and the sixth and seventh chapters are devoted to unpacking Mevlevi social capital as well as intellectual developments in later time periods. As such, the structure of the book encourages the reader to consider the Mevlevis as an emotional community that evolved both in terms of their power and their intellectual doctrines during the emergence of Ottoman society.

Although the book aims at covering transitions from 13th century Konya through 17th century Istanbul, Elias avoids the pitfall of a monotonous overview by foregrounding three pivotal moments: (1) the succession of Rumi's grandson, Ulu 'Arif Chelebi (d. 1320), to Mevlevi leadership after Rumi's death, (2) the rise of Mevlevi prominence in Ottoman society after the Ottoman conquest of Constantinople (16th and 17th centuries), and (3) the career of Isma'il Anqaravi

1 Jamal J. Elias, *After Rumi: The Mevlevis and Their World* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2025), 5. All subsequent citations from this text will henceforth be given as page numbers in-text.

(d. 1631), the scholar that Elias maintains is responsible for ongoing devotion to Rumi's *Masnawi* well into the 20th century. This periodization allows for the book's thematic foci on emotional community, Sufi praxis, and the role of Persian to be viewed as not static for the Mevlevi even if there are overarching trends—for example, on emotional community, Elias observes that there is an ongoing pattern of spiritual kinship between Mevlevi masters and their academic disciples wherein “the scholarly and literary authority of the disciple was legitimized by the charismatic spiritual credentials of the master” (p. 146), which is repeated across the three periods of Ulu ‘Arif Chelebi’s relationship with the biographer Aflaki al-‘Arifi (d. 1360), the 16th century Mevlevi master and founder of the Galata Mevlevi lodge Divane Mehmed Chelebi (d. 1544) with his student, the prolific reviver of the Mevlevi written tradition, Ibrahim Shahidi (d. 1550), and leader of the Konya lodge Bostan Chelebi (d. 1630) and his scholarly disciple Isma‘il Anqaravi. This shows how the Mevlevi’s self-presentation depended on this pattern of charismatic authority connected to scholarly production.

Indeed, the book’s attentiveness to this tripartite historical narrative allows for the theoretical frameworks of “emotional community” and “emotional style” to remain subordinated to textual analysis. In the introduction, Elias combines insights from the anthropologist William Reddy and the historian of medieval Europe B. H. Rosenwein to formulate an approach to emotional style that allows for change over time in how “new words and concepts enter religious vocabularies through changing patterns and valences” (p. 14).² Indeed, the flexibility of this approach allows for the book to avoid classifying Mevlevi emotions based on a static conception of genre, and the limited excursus into emotion in Islamic contexts in the introduction allows for insight on love as a “metacategory” for Sufi thought (p. 8). However, the book does not provide the philological texture one might expect to result from an approach that insists on the contextual significance of words used to signify structures of feeling—Elias points to examples such as *murīd* (aspirer) or *muhib* (lover) and suggests that we

2 B. H. Rosenwein, *Emotional Communities in the Early Middle Ages* (Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 2006); B. H. Rosenwein, *Generations of Feeling: A History of Emotions, 600–1700* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2016); W. M. Reddy, *The Navigation of Feeling: A Framework for the History of Emotions* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2001).

allow for Mevleviis to use multiple, overlapping terms, yet it remains unclear how and for whom Mevleviis allowed which words to apply over the course of the book's chronological arc (p. 13). In other words, the main thesis of the Mevlevi's self-presentation being founded on devotion to Rumi and his *Masnavi* is successfully proven through tracing meta-shifts in how Mevlevi thinkers related to their contemporaneous charismatic leaders as well as to Rumi as a foundational thinker and his text, yet micro-shifts in the specific vocabulary used for such devotion remains underexplored.

Moreover, the fact of who could participate in the Mevlevi community and how this shifts over time is pointed out but not interrogated by Elias. For example, the book provides details on the inclusion of Christians, some of whom did not convert, within the early Mevlevi community in Konya. This reflects the demographics of central Anatolia in the 12th and 13th centuries but nevertheless provides evidence of the significance of charismatic authority over and above doctrinal conformity (pp. 27-29). Yet by the time we reach Anqaravi's period, the question of who the Mevlevi community consists of fades as Elias instead foregrounds Shahidi and Anqaravi's emphasis on the text of the *Masnavi*, the former interested in linguistic and the latter in metaphysical preservation (p. 121). Is it simply reflective of demographic shifts in the early modern Ottoman world that the question of being simultaneously a Christian (or a Jew or a Zoroastrian) and a Mevlevi fades, or are there instances of non-Muslims continuing to show emotional attachment to Rumi, as in the modern revival of Rumi in US new age spirituality?³ What could this tell us about Mevlevi self-understanding, historically and today? Elias takes care to note how Mevleviis viewed other Sufi groups within their territories—Aflaki presents competition between *futuvvat* guilds and the Mevleviis, with the former being seen more as urban, militaristic masculine types who could, at times, become Mevleviis, while Bektashis and Bayramis appear to have interacted with the Mevleviis after the Ottoman conquest of Constantinople (pp. 86-93). Thus it was not the case that there was a progressive move towards a need to be a card-carrying Mevlevi to

3 Rozina Ali, "The Erasure of Islam from the Poetry of Rumi," *The New Yorker*, Jan. 5th, 2017, <https://www.newyorker.com/books/page-turner/the-erasure-of-islam-from-the-poetry-of-rumi>. For an overview of Rumi in the West prior to the 21st century, see Franklin Lewis, *Rumi: Past and Present, East and West* (London: Oneworld Publications, 2000), 449-644.

attend Mevlevi rituals. Further engagement with to what degree Mevlevis saw themselves as exclusively Muslim could ground Elias' illustrations of intra-Sufi engagement as well as provocatively speak back to the current moment.

Yet the book effectively discloses the significance of biological kinship for the Mevlevis even as Elias frames biological kinship as situated within a style of emotional kinship that could exceed the biological. For example, Elias unpacks how the early Mevlevi community was not yet routinized in its process of biological succession as the early biographer Aflaki describes Rumi's close emotional relationship with his grandson Ulu 'Arif in a way that legitimizes his succession over Rumi's son, Sultan Valad, or Rumi's disowned son 'Ala al-Din Muhammad, who conspired to kill Shams al-Din Tabrizi (pp. 53-54). Yet later Ottoman writers such as the first Ottoman Turkish biographer of Rumi, Lokman Dede (d. 1519), accepted hereditary succession, showing that the Mevlevis, like many religious communities, developed a mechanism for what Max Weber would term the routinization of charisma (p. 51).⁴ As the Mevlevis expanded after the Ottoman conquest of Constantinople, biological kinship remained central even as emotional bonds to the *Masnawi* and Persian opened the community outwards. Masculinity nevertheless remains a key aspect of belonging—a problem that Elias notes is concomitant with his sources stemming from a textual literate elite (p. 14) that name women, but do not often flesh out their lives (p. 58). Moreover, while Elias' method of reading Mevlevi self-presentation from a distance effectively allows for the book to not become too bogged down by questions over the factuality of biography or hagiography, engagement with the prevalence of *ṭabaqāt* or *tazkīra* literature in Islamic societies in the introduction could allow for a non-specialist reader to think with the texts Elias introduces as forms of self-presentation.⁵ Indeed, biographical dictionaries are a form of legitimization for many communities in the Islamic world be they formed

⁴ Max Weber, *The Theory of Social and Economic Organizations*, translated by A. M. Henderson and Talcott Parsons (New York: Free Press, 1964).

⁵ For more on the biographical tradition, see how Jawad A. Mojaddedi, *The Biographical Tradition in Sufism: The Ṭabaqāt Genre from al-Sulamī to Jāmī* (Surrey: Curzon Press, 2001) for example describes Jami's (d. 1492) revival of the genre, which develops from 'Aṭṭār's *Tazkīrat al-Alwiyā'*, as well as Paul Losensky's methodological approach in "The Creative Compiler: The Art of Rewriting in 'Aṭṭār's *Tazkīrat al-awliyā'*," in *The Necklace of the Pleiades*, ed. Franklin Lewis and Sunil Sharma (Leiden: Amsterdam University Press, 2010), 107-120.

around Sufism, poetry, or another type of profession, and engagement with the genre—without the aim to debunk it—could help place Mevlevi use of it in a wider network.

The question of *tazkira* production brings me to the book's larger argument about the role of Persian, which provides a clear narrative of Persian's gradual aestheticization in Anatolian and Ottoman contexts until its disappearance in the mid-17th century. Elias draws attention to the "liturgical status of the *Masnavi*," which compliments scholarship on the social function of *Masnavi* recitation and the office of the *Masnavi* reciter (*mesnevîhân*) in the Ottoman world (p. 167). Indeed, unlike the cultivation of Persian by court elites within palace circles who were interested in Hafez, 'Attar, and Sa'di, Rumi's *Masnavi* had a slightly wider audience of live recitation that gradually gave way to Ottoman Turkish commentary as literacy in the original diminished. The unique significance of the *Masnavi* comes to the fore in the latter half of the book, with Shahidi's Persian-Turkish lexicographical work *Tulfa-i Shāhidī* (*The Gift of Shahidi*) (completed 1514) serving as a key example of the *Masnavi*'s significance as it was intended to aid in understanding Rumi's *Masnavi* (p. 119). As such, the relationship between the emergence of Ottoman Turkish and classical Persian can be seen to be mediated by the *Masnavi* in early lexicographical works.

Given that the book thoroughly engages with ideas about the aestheticization of Persian in late Ottoman culture, it could be interesting to think further about the vernacular existence of Turkic languages alongside both an increasingly classed Persian and classical Arabic. Elias points to the usage of Greek by Rumi and Sultan Valad as a counterpoint to any argument that claims that their usage of Turkish signifies the birth of Anatolian Turkish literature (p. 33). Yet the relationship between Anatolian Turkish poets such as Yunus Emre (d. ca. 1320), authors prior to Shahidi speaking and writing in Turkish who rewrote Persian classics such as Gölsheri (d. 1317), and the circulation of Persian poetry as the heritage-speaking Persian emigre community became local in the latter 14th and early 15th century seems like a crucial nexus for further exploring vernacularity in Islamic cultures. Sheldon Pollock characterizes vernacularity as the moment of transition from "documentary" to "workly" roles: when Indic languages as well as romance languages were first used for literary purposes—what Pollock calls literarization—from 1000-1500, they displaced the importance of their

respective classical parents, Sanskrit and Latin. The linguistic distance between Arabic, Persian, and Turkish is obviously different from the linguistic proximity between Latin and romance languages, or Sanskrit and Indic languages, yet the earliest court poets of Persian justified their usage of Persian over Arabic with appeals to Persian being a spoken language of the people—the *shu‘ubiyya* movement of the 9th and 10th centuries, often seen as culminating in Ferdowsi’s (d. 1025) *Shahnameh*.⁶ If we can then say that by the time of Rumi’s *Masnavi* there was already a bifurcated use of Persian as both spoken and classical (i.e., as a language of written classics alone) in Anatolia, then can we say Persian was both a vernacular sister to and classical “parent” of Turkish? Elias addresses Persian’s well-known imprint on an elite Ottoman register, but what remains underexplored in terms of theories of vernacularity is the simultaneous Arabic imprint on both Ottoman directly and on Ottoman via Persian.⁷ In other words, if Persian should be, alongside classical Arabic, regarded as one of the parent classical languages to Ottoman, then Pollock’s model of one classical language giving birth to many vernaculars in the period 1000–1500 can be revised. Rather than seeing Ottoman authors as a part of one particular cosmopolis (the Latinate world, the Sanskritic world, for example), the density of multilingualism within the Islamic world, and particularly within Anatolian and Ottoman contexts from the 14th–17th centuries, may help break up the civilizational model that undergirds Pollock’s approach from within. Elias’ detailed work on Persian as a classical language remains focused on Mevlevi cultural production, and more comparative work on Persian and Arabic in Turkish contexts could speak back to dominant theoretical models.

On the opposite end of Elias’ chronological arc, the conclusion usefully points to disjunctions between Ottoman and South Asian contexts in terms of the fading of Persian. Drawing from Selim Kuru’s work, Elias points to a

6 On the *shu‘ubiyya* movement and its significance for early new Persian see, for example, Dick Davis, *Epic and Sedition: The Case of Ferdowsi’s Shāhnāmah* (Fayetteville: University of Arkansas Press, 1992), 15–18.

7 Sheldon Pollock, *The Language of the Gods in the World of Men: Sanskrit, Culture, and Power in Premodern India* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2006). Alexander Beecroft describes how Persian eventually grew to displace or usurp to some degree the cosmopolitan language (Arabic) with which it found itself in competition in *An Ecology of World Literature: From Antiquity to the Present Day* (New York: Verso, 2015).

shared nostalgia for Timurid court culture during the reign of Husayn Bayqara (r. 1469-1506) between the Ottomans, Mughals, Safavids, and Uzbeks.⁸ The book's particular argument about the role of the *Masnavi* as a liturgical text in preserving Persian until the mid-17th century is useful, therefore, in drawing a contrast with a similar process that does not occur until the 19th and early 20th century in South Asia (p. 173). Recent work on the Persianate in South Asia by Alexander Jabbari and in Central Asia by Sam Hodgkin has insisted on the ongoing tendrils of Persianate aesthetics even as Persian as a language itself is displaced by nationalizing frameworks.⁹ While this approach effectively displaces nationalism, it has been critiqued for duplicating a nostalgia perhaps latent within the category of the Persianate itself.¹⁰ I appreciate that Elias and Kuru bring forth the social milieu in which Persian became aestheticized, namely that of urban elites, and it prevents a totalizing reach back to Shahab Ahmed's "Balkans-to-Bengal" complex as anything uniform. Instead, we are given a succinct and well substantiated claim about the overlapping mystical and courtly usages of Persian in 16th and 17th century Ottoman worlds.

On the book's arguments about Sufism, Elias effectively challenges both Anglophone and Turkish scholarship by insisting that we rid ourselves of the language of "heterodoxy" and "orthodoxy." Indeed, the chronological arc of the book aids Elias' claim that "there is little in common between the construction of religious identity in fourteenth-century Anatolia and the Ottoman Empire in the eighteenth century" (p. 75). Debunking Anglophone assumptions about antinomianism is a major thrust of chapter four writ large, and despite his admiration for Abdülbâki Gölpınarlı's scholarship, Elias notes that he perpetuated "a Sunni-centric view of Sufi normativity" (p. 135). Yet despite this notable unpacking of terms that are historically unverifiable, Elias does not engage with more nuanced scholarly approaches in the study of Sufism today—from

8 Selim Kuru, "The Literature of Rum: The Making of a Literary Tradition (1450–1600)," in *The Cambridge History of Turkey*, ed. Suraiya N. Faroqhi and Kate Fleet (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2012), 548–592.

9 Sam Hodgkin, *Persianate Verse and the Poetics of Eastern Internationalism* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2023); Alexander Jabbari, *The Making of Persianate Modernity: Language and Literary History between Iran and India* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2023).

10 Alexander Jabbari, "Persianate Dialectics," *Comparative Literature Studies* 61, no. 4 (2024): 608–613, and the entire forum. <https://doi.org/10.5325/complitstudies.61.4.0608>.

Omid Safi's now dated framing of *baraka* as about Sufi political power to Shahab Ahmed's imagining of Islam as a tradition of ambiguity through Hafez's poetics of wine-drinking and homoeroticism and the Sufi reception of them, the study of Sufism has evolved beyond perspectives that seek to pin it down upon any one way of being.¹¹ If any reader is to take away from the book that the Mevlevis saw themselves as emotionally attached to Rumi and his *Masnavi* firstly and to the other Islamic commitments they had secondly, then Elias succeeds in developing a set of historical examples that effectively counter presentist oversimplifications of Sufism.

Yet the book's attentiveness to its sources at times detracts from rethinking its theoretical interventions, and the intervention on Sufism in particular could be enhanced by scholarship attentive to gender. Margaret Malamud's paradigmatic approach to masculinity in master-disciple relationships, for example, could have helped with shifting emphasis away from a 1980s women's studies approach of retrieving women—although Elias' detailed accounts of female teachers such as Khushliqa Qunavi and her cohort of male disciples are noteworthy (p. 58)—and towards an approach that also incorporates Mevlevi masculinity as part of both their metaphysics and the social power they wielded in Ottoman society.¹² What does it mean that the Mevlevis hold Rumi's masculine authority alongside depictions of him nursing his son, Sultan Valad (p. 48)? How can we understand masculinity as a part of charismatic authority, cultivated both by Mevlevis and their Ottoman patrons, especially as the latter legitimized their expansion through adopting astrological-mystical titles such as *sahib-qiran* (lord of the conjunction)? Discussion of how mystical masculinity impacted Mevlevi self-presentation in terms of their metaphysics as well as their social capital awaits further study.

Overall, the book offers a view of Mevlevi self-understandings that is not confessional, but that is interested in the Mevlevis as both an intellectual and

11 Omid Safi, *The Politics of Knowledge in Premodern Islam: Negotiating Ideology and Religious Inquiry* (Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, 2006), 125-158; Shahab Ahmed, *What Is Islam?: The Importance of Being Islamic* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2015), 32.

12 Margaret Malamud, "Gender and Spiritual Self-Fashioning: The Master-Disciple Relationship in Classical Sufism," *Journal of the American Academy of Religion* 64, no. 1 (1996): 89-117. Additionally, on masculinity and metaphysics, see Mahdi Tourage, "Phallogocentric Esotericism in a Tale from Jalal al-Din Rumi's *Masnavi-yi Ma'navi*," *Iranian Studies* 39, no. 1 (2006): 47-70.

social force in the Ottoman world through the 17th century. The arguments about Persian and Sufism that appear along the way enhance this central claim, further grounding the Mevlevis in a social milieu in which they had power to actively shape. By being simultaneously interested in the Mevlevis as both political actors and as intellectuals, Elias shows how the Mevlevis' staying power is connected to their internal sense of their being an emotional community founded upon charismatic authority and a charismatic text. Observing Mevlevi self-presentation from a distance, the book compliments existing scholarship on Rumi by insisting on reception as a critical approach to communal self-understanding.